

PROBLEMS OF ACCELERATING DIGITALIZATION IN THE ECONOMY OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This paper examines key issues of digitalization in Uzbekistan's economy, analyzes literature and strategic documents on digital transformation, and presents research results along with recommendations for strengthening the impact of digitalization on the country's socio-economic development.

Key words: Market economy, digitalization, digital transformation, e-government, statistics, digital technologies, ICT.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, a lot of attention is paid to the development of digital technologies. Scientists are confident that the development of technologies in the future will affect all relationships between people, the economy, society and the world as a whole. The terms "digitalization", "digital economy" are considered in relation to both theory and practice of the world community. Digitalization can be defined as the introduction of information technology in all areas of activity in systems of different levels, including the economy. Hence, the digital economy stands out. Digital economy is an economic activity in which the key factor of production is data in digital form, processing of large volumes and the use of analysis results, which, compared with traditional forms of management, can significantly increase the efficiency of various types of production, technology, equipment, storage, sale, delivery of goods. In Uzbekistan, a number of measures have been taken towards the formation, implementation and development of digitalization as a new innovative component of the economy, including the adoption of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the State Program for the Implementation of the Action Strategy for Five Priority Areas of Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021", the main focus of which is the formation of an innovative model for the development of the economy of Uzbekistan. Further, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyev dated July 3, 2018 No. 11113832 "On measures to develop the digital economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan" was adopted. In recent years, the following documents have also been adopted: the Strategy "DIGITAL UZBEKISTAN-2030", the Decree of the President dated July 24, 2021 No. UP-6268 "On Amendments and Additions, as well as Recognition as Invalid of Certain Acts of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 5, 2020 No. UP-6079 "On the approval of the Strategy "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" and measures for its effective implementation"), which allow us to determine the prospects for the use of information technology in the country. [1]. In this regard, the authors of this work wanted to determine their attitude to the digitalization of the economy of Uzbekistan.

Literature review

Currently, there is great interest in the world in digital economics. Thus, Russian economists Glazyev S.Yu., Repeyev A.P., Savin N.V. consider the digital economy as the basis for the transition to a new

technological order, increasing the efficiency of economic processes.[2] Among Uzbek economists: Abdullaev O.M., Zhumanazarov K., Yangiboyev B.Ya., believe that it is associated with the development of information technology, therefore it is advisable to consider the digital economy as a development process associated with technology, economic agents and the global Internet, but this is not enough, since the digital economy is, first of all, the development of digital information technology.[3]

Research Methodology

The study employs abstract, mathematical, and statistical methods.

Analysis and Results

An important point in this area is Uzbekistan's place in international rankings. Thus, according to the Telecommunication Infrastructure Index (TII), which is formed on the basis of the following indicators per 100 residents of the country: the number of Internet users and fixed telephone lines, as well as mobile subscribers, wireless broadband and fixed broadband networks. Since 2016, Uzbekistan has improved its performance on this index from 0.246 to 0.472.

The ICT Development Index (IDI), which was last compiled by the International Telecommunication Union based on the results of 2017 among 176 countries of the world. The IDI index consists of 11 statistical indicators reflecting the availability of ICT, the degree of its use and practical skills in using ICT by the population. A new methodology for compiling the IDI index is currently being developed. In the latest IDI rating, Uzbekistan moved up 8 positions compared to 2016 and took 95th place (index - 4.9) among 176 countries of the world. **The Global Cybersecurity Index** is also compiled by the International Telecommunication Union and assesses the level of state commitments in five areas: legal measures, technical measures, organizational measures, capacity development and international cooperation. Since 2016, Uzbekistan has improved its performance in this rating from 0.1471 to 0.666 and moved up from 93rd to 52nd place among 175 countries. **The E-Government Development Index (EGDI)** is compiled by the Department of Economic and Social Affairs of the United Nations Secretariat based on the indicators of three sub-indices: development of online government services, telecommunications infrastructure and human capital development. According to the indicators of this index, Uzbekistan has improved its indicators from 0.54 to 0.67 since 2016 and ranks 87th among 193 countries.[4] In the global digitalization index Global Digitalization Index 2024 (GDI), Uzbekistan ranked 60th out of 77 countries, scoring 32.7 points out of a possible 120. This index reflects the level of digitalization in different countries and shows the relationship between digital technologies and the level of gross domestic product (GDP). The study divides countries into three groups: leaders, developing and beginners. Uzbekistan is included in the category of beginner countries, demonstrating an initial level of maturity in the field of information and communication technologies (ICT) and the economy [5].

Conclusion

However, this does not mean that there are no problems associated with its further development. In this regard, we would like to draw attention to the need for further development of an effective mechanism for enhancing digitalization for all business entities in the economy of Uzbekistan. In this regard, we consider it necessary to take into account the following recommendations:

- formation and increase in the competitiveness of modern infrastructure in the field of telecommunications and informatization; digitalization of the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- develop partnerships with international IT companies to attract investment in the digitalization of the country's economy (European and Asian countries);
- strengthen the country's capabilities to ensure cybersecurity and personal data protection, increase the level of digital literacy of the population through various forms of deepening knowledge of economic, information, communication literacy..

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